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COMPRESSION ULTRASOUND ELASTOGRAPHY IN THE DIAGNOSIS OF BENIGN AND MALIGNANT BREAST DISEASES

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Annotation: In the course of the study, the possibilities of compression ultrasound elastography in the diagnosis of benign and malignant breast diseases were determined, data were obtained indicating a high degree of correlation of the density of formation with the nature of structural changes in breast tissue, it was determined that the use of compression elastography is advisable not only for the diagnosis of palpable formations, but also for the diagnosis of complex cases of non-palpable formations and is an additional method of research when making a correct diagnosis.

Keywords: mammary gland, ultrasound diagnostics, compression elastography

КОМПРЕССИОННАЯ УЛЬТРАЗВУКОВАЯ ЭЛАСТОГРАФИЯ В ДИАГНОСТИКЕ ДОБРОКАЧЕСТВЕННЫХ И ЗЛОКАЧЕСТВЕННЫХ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЙ МОЛОЧНОЙ ЖЕЛЕЗЫ

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Аннотация: В процессе исследования определены возможности компрессионной ультразвуковой эластографии в диагностике доброкачественных и злокачественных заболеваний молочной железы, получены данные, свидетельствующие о высокой степени корреляции плотности образования с характером структурных изменений в ткани молочной железы, определено, что применение компрессионной эластографии целесообразно не только для диагностики пальпируемых образований, но и для диагностики сложных случаев непальпируемых образований и является дополнительным методом исследования при постановке правильного диагноза.

Ключевые слова: молочная железа, ультразвуковая диагностика, компрессионная эластография

Relevance. Breast cancer ranks first in the structure of oncological morbidity and mortality of the female population in the world [1].

More than 1 million new cases of breast cancer are registered annually in the world, and more than 400 thousand people die from the disease. In Europe, the annual incidence of breast cancer is 109.9 per 100 thousand women, mortality is 38.4 per 100 thousand women, and the indicators vary greatly in different geographical areas [1, 2].

The choice of an adequate treatment strategy for patients depends on the timely diagnosis and correct assessment of the prevalence of the

tumor process. Of particular relevance is the widespread introduction of various visualization methods [3].

The initial diagnostic algorithm for the examination of patients includes clinical examination, X-ray mammography and ultrasound examination of the mammary glands, which is not always sufficient for a full interpretation of the patient's condition, especially in the case of non-palpable mammary gland formations, ambiguity in the interpretation of visualization during structural rearrangements, with increased density of gland tissue. Clinical examination has low sensitivity indicators, especially with non-palpable formations. With mammography and ultrasound, there are discrepancies in the scant visual and morphological manifestations of the process. With traditional ultrasound, Dopplerography provides clarifying information. In early malignant lesions, these are: high blood flow rate and atypical Doppler curves [3].

In this regard, the introduction of new technologies for early diagnosis of breast pathology is relevant. One of the methods that can increase the informativeness of breast ultrasound is a new technology – elastography. This method is based on the assessment of tissue stiffness. There are compression elastography and shear wave elastography.

The purpose of the work. Determination of the possibilities of compression ultrasound elastography in the diagnosis of benign and malignant breast diseases.

Materials and methods of research. 122 women aged from 27 to 63 years (average age 45.5 years) with breast pathology were examined: 38 (32 %) breast cancer patients, 84 (68 %) women with benign pathology. The patients were examined on the basis of the medical institution "Grodno University Clinic".

The research methods included clinical examination, X-ray mammography, standard ultrasound, a complex of interventional radiology technologies with subsequent morphological verification.

Ultrasound with the use of compression elastography was included in the comprehensive examination of all patients, which was performed on a Toshiba SSA 790A ultrasound scanner (Japan) using special software for sonoelastographic reconstruction. The compression elastographic image is realized with moderate compression by the sensor of the studied area in the form of color coding of elasticity in the selected zone and is superimposed on the B-mode images. The elasticity of the fabrics is determined and

displayed in certain colors on a normal B-mode screen. The denser fabric structure is displayed in shades of blue, while easily compressible elastic areas are marked with a red color scale.

Initially, the formation was evaluated in the standard B-mode, as well as using color and energy Doppler mapping, pulse-wave Dopplerography. After the compression elastography mode was activated, the zone of interest was selected depending on the size and position of the formation. The elastogram provides information about the comparative density of the tissues included in the area of interest. In this regard, it is necessary to include unchanged surrounding tissues in the area of interest for the correct distribution of differences in the density of the formation and surrounding tissues.

Depending on the degree of density of formation and infiltration of surrounding tissues, elastographic images are classified into 5 main types. In type 1, the formation is uniformly colored green, as are the surrounding tissues, in type 2, the formation has a mosaic structure with denser areas of blue and elastic areas of green. The central part of the type 3 formation is colored blue, the peripheral parts are green. In type 4, the formation is denser and is completely mapped in blue, in type 5, the formation and surrounding tissues are colored blue. In addition to the above types, there are 2 more types of images: a three-layer type, characteristic of liquid-containing structures, and a mosaic type with green and red areas.

Results and their discussion. Qualitative criteria of compression elastography in benign diseases were presented by the following types of elastograms:

The 1st type of elastogram in which the formation has the same ability to deform as the unchanged surrounding breast tissue was obtained with fibroadenoma, nodular mastopathy (lobular hyperplasia), lipoma, cyst. This type did not allow to establish the nosological form of the disease, but in 100 % of cases it testified to the benign nature of the growth of education.

The 2nd type of elastogram, in which the formation is somewhat denser than the surrounding tissues, was obtained with fibroadenoma, nodular mastopathy, infiltrative stage of mastitis, benign leaf-shaped tumor, lipogranuloma, atheroma, intra-flow papilloma, cyst. This type also did not allow to establish the nosological form of the disease, however, in 93 % of cases it testified to the benign nature of the growth of education.

The 6th type of elastogram was observed in all cases with a breast cyst. A three-layer image of this type of elastogram arises due to an elastographic artifact, thus, liquid-containing structures are mapped by a three-layer type of elastogram.

The 7th type of elastogram was characteristic of formations with thick liquid contents, it was detected in mastitis in the abscess phase and in cysts with thick contents, which in 100 % of cases indicated the benign nature of the detected changes.

Compression elastographic images of malignant formations differed from elastograms of benign formations due to a higher density of nodes and infiltration of surrounding tissues. In case of malignant neoplasms, the 4th and 5th types of elastograms were determined in 87 % (in 33 cases out of 38). At the same time, the 1st, 6th and 7th types in this group of patients were not identified even once. In the 4th type of elastogram, it was most characteristic of solid, limited-growing carcinomas. With the 5th type of elastogram, the formation and surrounding tissues had a high density, which reflected the infiltration of interstitial space by cancer cells (tumors with a scyrrhous type of growth).

The data of compression sonoelastography corresponded to the pathomorphological conclusion in 106 observations. When evaluating qualitative sonoelastographic criteria, the sensitivity of the method was 73.7 %, specificity – 92.8 %, accuracy – 86.9 %, prognosticality of a positive result – 82.3 %, prognosticality of a negative result – 88.6 %. When evaluating quantitative sonoelastographic criteria, the sensitivity of the method was 78.9 %, specificity – 95.2 %, accuracy – 90.1 %. The determination of the sensitivity, specificity and accuracy of X-ray mammography, ultrasound and elastography in clarifying the nature of the growth of education has shown that traditional mammography and ultrasound can identify the formation, and in combination with sonoelastography to clarify its nature.

Conclusions. As a result of the study, data were obtained indicating a high degree of correlation between the density of education and the nature of structural changes in breast tissue. Malignant diseases were characterized by a high degree of tissue stiffness, which was reflected on the compression elastogram in the form of mapping in blue shades, benign formations were mapped in green or red.

The use of compression elastography is advisable not only for the diagnosis of palpable formations, but also for the diagnosis of complex cases of non-palpable formations and is an additional method of investigation when making a correct diagnosis.

Bibliography

[1] Alekhovich A.V. Modern dynamics of morbidity and mortality in the population of the Republic of Belarus and the Russian Federation in connection with breast cancer / A.V. Alekhovich, T.I. Zimatkina, A.S. Aleksandrovich // Radiation and ecological medicine: modern problems, a look into the future: Sat. materials Rep. scientific-practical. conf. with international participation, Grodno, 29-30 Sept. 2022 – Grodno, 2022. 33-37 p.

[2] Zimatkina T.I. Current trends in morbidity and mortality in the Republic of Belarus in connection with malignant neoplasms of different localization / T.I. Zimatkina, A.S. Aleksandrovich // Radiation and ecological medicine: modern problems, a look into the future: Sat. materials Rep. scientific-practical. conf. with international participation, Grodno, 29-30 Sept. 2022 – Grodno, 2022. 124-130 p.

[3] Markevich N.B. Analysis of the results of mammographic screening and medical prevention of breast cancer in the population of Grodno and the Grodno region / N.B. Markevich, A.S. Aleksandrovich, T.I. Zimatkina, I.A. Aleksandrovich // Radiation and ecological medicine: modern problems, a look into the future: Sat. materials Rep. scientific-practical. conf. with international participation, Grodno, 29-30 Sept. 2022 – Grodno, 2022. 167-170 p.

Список литературы (перевод)

[1] Алехнович А.В. Современная динамика заболеваемости и смертности населения Республики Беларусь и Российской Федерации в связи с раком молочной железы / А.В. Алехнович, Т.И. Зиматкина, А.С. Александрович // Радиационная и экологическая медицина: современные проблемы, взгляд в будущее: сб. материалов Респ. науч.-практ. конф. с междунар. участием, Гродно, 29-30 сент. 2022 г. – Гродно, 2022. 33-37 с.

[2] Зиматкина Т.И. Современные тенденции заболеваемости и смертности Республики Беларусь в связи с злокачественными новообразованиями разной локализации / Т.И. Зиматкина, А.С. Александрович // Радиационная и экологическая медицина: современные проблемы, взгляд в будущее: сб. материалов Респ. науч.-практ. конф. с междунар. участием, Гродно, 29-30 сент. 2022 г. – Гродно, 2022. 124-130 с.

[3] Маркевич Н.Б. Анализ результатов маммографического скрининга и медицинской профилактики рака молочной железы у населения г. Гродно и Гродненской области / Н.Б. Маркевич, А.С. Александрович, Т.И. Зиматкина, И.А. Александрович // Радиационная и экологическая медицина: современные проблемы, взгляд в будущее: сб. материалов Респ. науч.-практ. конф. с междунар. участием, Гродно, 29-30 сент. 2022 г. – Гродно, 2022. 167-170 с.

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